

OPEN**Socio Economic Impact of Covid 19 Pandemic**Dr Ashu Tomar ¹

Covid 19 pandemic impacted every person of the world. The life of every human being is affected by it. The paper will carry out to find out the following: covid pandemic, social impact, economic impact, impact on education and conclusion. Aim: To take step forward towards the impact of covid 19 pandemic. Future Scope: Finding more ways for studying pros and cons. Integration of human being. The paper attempts to study all the pros and cons of covid 19 impact in all the aspects of life. It has brought stand still in the life of all.

Keywords: COVID-19; pandemic, online, virtual

Introduction

Covid Pandemic has impacted every aspect of human life. Coronavirus disease is an infectious disease caused by a newly discovered coronavirus. Most people infected with the COVID-19 virus experience mild to moderate respiratory illness and recover without requiring special treatment. A virus is a very small (microscopic) type of germ that can cause an infection in throat. It spreads in the world.

The economic and social disruption caused by the pandemic is devastating. Millions of people are at risk of falling into extreme poverty. The coronavirus pandemic has reached almost every country in the world. Its spread has left national economies and businesses at loss.

Impact of online classes on socialization.

Socialization refers to the process of interaction through which the growing individual learns the habits, attitudes, values and beliefs of the social group by which he/ she is interacting.

Schools provide both formal and informal contexts to the students. The formal context is the one provided in the classroom wherein the content of socialization is determined by the curriculum and the teaching learning process. Informal context can be perceived in the interpersonal relations of students with teachers, seniors, juniors and the peer group.

A teacher can boost the process of socialization in children by modeling behaviour, communicating expectations and buyer enforcing positive behaviour. As facilitator of student's socialization into the learning environment, the teacher has the potential for bringing desirable change in behaviour. His/ her role expands beyond that of instructor while he/ she is engaged in student socialization.

The senior, junior and peer group relationships also help in development of adaptive skills for emphasising proper socialisation process.

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The pandemic had a major impact on socialisation of children as Traditional teaching learning process which used to take place in a classroom has been transformed into a virtual mode (Muthuprasad et al 2021). The students and teachers meet in a virtual classroom on a daily basis and continue their teaching learning process. Both are sitting in front of the screens for most part of their day. The impact of the pandemic on socialisation is huge, it is visible in their behaviour, physical health and mental health but virtual classes are still providing some sort of interaction and hence an opportunity of socialisation for children (Singh et al, 2020).

Students in online learning environments interact with classmates on a daily basis, just like in traditional classrooms. Additionally live lessons can be hosted where students and teachers connect using an online video chat. But the socialization doesn't stop there. Because students don't sit in a physical classroom together every day, they're encouraged to find ways to socialize outside of their live lessons. This can be anything from group chats to virtual study groups, giving students more time to strengthen their friendships.

One of the biggest ways students socialize is through clubs, societies. Most traditional schools, colleges have a set list of clubs they offer. Online classes can have these as well, and students meet on a weekly basis using online video chat. To create an even stronger community, and increase student involvement, schools and colleges can encourage their students to present their own club ideas for implementation.

The majority of student activities at traditional schools revolve around things like group activities, educational tours, co-curricular activities. Online schools, colleges can also offer similar activities. For example, monthly meet ups for students and staff, ranging from small celebrations to campus tours and from online co-curricular activities to group projects and special assemblies. This gives students time to

plan in advance for activities and interact with class mates.

Being an online learner doesn't mean giving up the social aspect of your life. In many ways, online school and colleges will give you the tools to socialize in more ways.

Gendered impact of COVID-19

The economic crisis induced by the COVID-19 pandemic led to unprecedented job losses for both women and men but the disproportionate hit that COVID-19 dealt to female workers is set to endure with the men's employment recovering more quickly than women's, according to the international labour organization (Gromico, 2021).

A deep rooted patriarchy and gender stereotype has already promoted gender division of labour, which is the reason for today's inequality between men and women. The inequalities between women and men in the world of work have been exacerbated during the COVID-19 pandemic and will persist in the near future as well. Even though the projected jobs growth in 2021 for women exceeds that of men, it will, nonetheless, be insufficient to bring women back to pre-pandemic employment levels.

According to an estimated report of international labour organization, 13 million fewer women will be working this year than in 2019 (Gromico, 2021). Men, on the other hand have succeeded in recouping the crisis induced losses. In the contemporary world the major reason for women vulnerable position is their economic dependence. The pandemic impacted woman's job and this again will put women in a position where they will be economically dependent on others. Hence, more vulnerable to exploitation. Their role in decision-making power will reduce and patriarchy will be on rise again.

Bridging this gap is extremely important. The governments should enact policies that place gender equality at the core of the recovery effort and focus on

job creation and retention that will benefit women. Following steps should be taken: -

- Investing in the care economy because the health, social work and education sectors are key generators of jobs for women.
- Working towards universal access to comprehensive, adequate and sustainable social protection.
- Promoting equal pay for equal work.
- Eliminating violence and harassment in the world of work.
- Promoting women's participation in decision-making bodies.
- Promoting work from home opportunities for women.
- Making women aware about technology and organising seminars or workshops so that women can know how to use technology and get employment.
- Organising some online vocational courses, online educational courses and skill development programs.

In the past a lot of steps have been taken for the upliftment and empowerment of women. But due to this pandemic some of our efforts has been reversed and now focusing on upliftment and empowerment should be with more rigor and we should try our best to bridge this gap as soon as possible.

Impact on health

Corona pandemic has affected every aspect of human life including children. Whether it's the mental health, physical health or a combination of both – the children have had their own share of health problems during this pandemic phase.

Increasing eyesight problems with frequent headaches are attributed to prolonged screen time. In addition, increasing anxiety and depression due to home confinement along with sleep disorders are also on the rise. I myself suffered a lot of pain in the eyes due to

long hours of online classes. Children attending online classes at home are not bound to have classroom professionalism. Hence, their physical health is deteriorating too in many aspects.

Lack of physical activities: I cannot remember the last day when I was out in the park or in the ground or in the college playing something or enjoying at least in the last two years. Obesity in children is on the rise either due to lack of outdoor physical activities or due to binge eating and easy availability of junk food at home.

Children are losing their muscle mass and adding fat which is going to affect their growth. Research has shown that the more physically active a child is during the growing period the better is their physical and mental health for the next 3-4 decades of life (Booth et al, 2012). Children by being physically inactive are also losing their muscle tone thereby finding it very difficult to cope up with sports when they resume in future due to muscle rigidity. Physical activities play a large role in Calcium and Vitamin D levels of the body (Wiciński et al, 2019). Deficiencies are on the rise in recent times in children and their reasons are very obvious.

Deficiencies of Calcium and Vitamin D: Apart from lack of physical activity, lack of sunlight exposure and poor diet also contributes to Calcium and Vitamin D deficiencies. Muscle cramps, spasms and strains/tears are common with trivial injuries / bad postures when a child is having severe deficiencies (Wiciński et al, 2019).

Poor ergonomics: Unlike classrooms, the children are not bound to follow good ergonomics at home. Taking online classes on bed and sofas are one of the commonest reasons that we can attribute to recent rise on back pains or fibromyalgic pains. I am currently suffering from repetitive strain injury in hands due to overuse of mobile for typing and other work.

Parents, teachers and we need to be cautious as well as to make sure that their family remain fit and healthy. Wearing face masks, social distancing and emphasis on personal hygiene are a must for all of us. Create a classroom atmosphere at home to respect and maintain professionalism and good ergonomics. Set screen time for mobiles and tabs after class hours and encourage children to avoid electronic devices. Healthy muscles need good hydration and healthy food habits. Keep away from binge eating and junk foods. 30-45 minutes of sunlight exposure with a minimum of 1-1.5 hours of exertion/rigorous physical activity like gym/ aerobics/ yoga or outdoor physical activities whenever feasible is a must for all growing children.

Impact of COVID-19 on examinations

The education sector has gone through deep structural changes since the major outbreak of the deadly Covid-19 virus. While classroom teaching has changed drastically, the most wide-ranging immediate impact has been on our system of assessment and examination. The CBSE board exams now stand cancelled. Many state boards have followed suit. While the government rightly prioritised student safety in its decision to cancel the exam, we must examine the likely repercussions of the decision on the students and where possible how to mitigate the negative impact.

The cancellation of board exams affects the entry of students in some undergraduate courses more than other courses. In India there is a well-defined structure of competitive exams at the state and national level in place for engineering and medical courses. Students pursuing these streams are firmly in control of their future. Their performance in the exams such as JEE, NEET and other Common Entrance Tests will determine their entry into a university of their choice. Students who pursue the courses such as Arts or Humanities face a lot of uncertainty. Universities such as Delhi University, Madras University and many

others rely heavily on the marks scored in the Board Examination to grant admission. The cancellation of these examinations now puts the onus on the Universities to start expanding the criteria for their selection process such as looking at the overall profile of the student, seeing the historical academic performance, and even consider introducing entrance examinations for admissions.

While many educators and students expressed relief that their concerns about health and safety were addressed, others are apprehensive about whether the move can fix the uncertainties that have plagued the education system since the onset of the pandemic.

There are also concerns about how the academic performance of students will be evaluated now. What about those who had worked hard to improve their previous scores? Will percentage discrepancies end up impacting the future prospects of millions of students? Also, there are some students who just avoid studying without any exam pressure so that students found themselves relaxed but at later they have to bear the consequences in the next promoted class.

The dependence on technology for learning and recreation is almost complete and social interactions, outdoor activities have been severely curtailed. Daily routines have been disrupted and home confinement is likely to impact mental health. According to WHO, 50 per cent of all mental health conditions can surface as early as 14 years of age, these often go untreated and undetected (WHO, 2021)."

In sum, while it has been a challenging year for education, it has also forced educators to think deeply on the fundamentals of learning and assessment. It has also led to the rapid development of technological tools to aid learning. As we slowly step out of this pandemic, these learnings and advances will pave the way for more relevant learning frameworks, better-skilled teachers, more engaged learners and positive learning outcomes.

Impact of Covid-19 on education

As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, so do the risks we face. The COVID-19 pandemic has not stopped at national borders. It has affected people regardless of nationality, level of education, income or gender. But the same has not been true for its consequences, which have hit the most vulnerable hardest.

Education is no exception. Students from privileged backgrounds, supported by their parents and eager and able to learn, could find their way past closed school doors to alternative learning opportunities. Those from disadvantaged backgrounds often remained shutting out when their schools shut down. This crisis has exposed the many inadequacies and inequities. In our education systems – from access to the broadband and computers needed for online education. The supportive environments needed to focus on learning up to the misalignment between resources and needs. The lockdowns in response to COVID-19 have interrupted conventional schooling with nationwide closure of educational institutions in India.

In Oct. 2019, the World Bank introduced the concept of learning poverty. This is a way to put a face to a name when it comes to the learning crisis that children and adults across the world face every day. According to the World Bank, learning poverty occurs when one is unable to read and comprehend simple text by the age of ten. Even before COVID-19 which forced a massive closure of schools around the globe, the world was in the middle of a learning crisis that threatened efforts to build human capital—the skills and know-how needed for the jobs of the future. More than half of 10-year-old children in low- and middle-income countries either had failed to learn to read with comprehension or were out of school entirely. Across the globe, students are underprepared or unprepared, teachers are ill-equipped or unqualified, and administrative institutions lack the organisation to enforce high standards of teaching.

With the arrival of covid-19 this situation further degrades into its new lower levels. Temporary educational institutions closures in this pandemic, kept billions of students out of schools, one can imagine the intensity of loss children suffer in their learning process. The negative impact of the unprecedented global economic contraction on family incomes has increased school dropouts. Marginalized groups are likely to fall further behind. Girls are facing increased risk of adolescent pregnancy and early marriage during the pandemic. And children with disabilities, ethnic minorities, refugees, and displaced populations are less likely to access suitable remote learning materials and to return to school post-crisis.

However, in response to the pandemic, education systems have been forced to rapidly implement innovations in remote learning at scale. To reach as many children and youth as possible, they have used multi-modal remote learning approaches that combine online resources with radio, TV, mobile, as well as printed materials for the most vulnerable. However, the huge digital divides – from connectivity to digital skills – and inequalities in the quality of parental support and home learning environments is amplifying learning inequality.

Going forward, as now schools/universities are reopening, educational systems will need to be more flexible and adapt to the student's needs. We will need to reimagine their educational systems and to use the opportunity presented by the pandemic to build back better and enhance learning opportunities in order to curb down learning poverty.

Conclusion

Covid pandemic has affected the whole world. It has impacted every sphere of life. Large number of people got vaccinated daily in every country to save public from covid pandemic. There is the need to come out of this pandemic fear and live the life with the normal

routine as people used to live earlier. Though the virtual communication has replaced face to face communication and other ways came into new norm. It is only a way out for accomplishing the task in this covid situation.

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